

IDEA Code of Conduct

Neil Davies, Tetiaroa Society, UC Berkeley Gump South Pacific Research Station

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The following is adapted from the Toronto Statement on Prepublication International Data Sharing.¹

Participants in the IDEA Consortium agree to abide by the following principles:

Respect the Privacy, Ethical, and Legal rights of anyone, including Indigenous peoples², who might be adversely affected by the collection, distribution, use or reuse of data, samples or derived information and knowledge. Apply consent, confidentiality, anonymization and other ethical considerations, where appropriate.

Rapid prepublication data release to the IDEA Consortium (e.g., through one of its regional chapters such as the Tetiaroa IDEA), which is a program with the following characteristics:

- Large scale (requiring significant resources over time) and broad utility
- Creating reference data sets
- Associated with community buy-in

Coordinating nodes (e.g., Tetiaroa Society for the Tetiaroa IDEA) should facilitate the specification of data-release policies and compliance with agreed Data Management Plans by:

- Explicitly informing applicants of data-release requirements, especially mandatory prepublication data release
- Ensuring that evaluation of data release plans is part of the peer-review process
- Proactively establishing analysis plans and timelines for projects releasing data prepublication
- Fostering investigator-initiated prepublication data release
- Helping to develop appropriate consent, security, access and governance mechanisms that protect research participants while encouraging prepublication data release
- Providing long-term support of databases

Project leaders should state their intentions and enable analyses of their data or material samples by:

- Informing data/sample users (e.g., through a ‘marker paper’ at initiation of the project) about the data/samples being generated, data standards and quality, planned analyses, timelines, and relevant contact information
- Providing relevant metadata and documentation that will assist other researchers in reproducing and/or independently analyzing the data, while protecting privacy and other ethical, legal, and social aspects concerning individuals and communities

¹**Prepublication data sharing** Toronto International Data Release Workshop Authors Nature **461**, 168-170 (10 September 2009) doi:%5B10.1038/461168a](doi.org/10.1038/461168a)

²Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, and Ethics - CARE principles for Indigenous data governance. GIDA <https://www.Gida-Global.Org/care>

- Ensuring that all participants in their Project are informed that their data will be shared with other scientists in the IDEA Consortium and the associated terms
- Publishing their initial global analyses in a timely fashion
- Providing a copy of their data, protocols, software and other outputs, in an easily retrievable form and with appropriate metadata and documentation that facilitates usage of both pre-processed and processed data (e.g., following FAIR data principles)
- Ensuring the long-term maintenance of these resources (e.g., through deposition in appropriate repositories and collections).

Data analysts/users should freely analyze released prepublication data or samples and act responsibly in publishing their analyses by:

- Respecting the scientific etiquette that allows data producers to publish the first global analyses of their data set
- Reading the citable document(s) associated with the project (e.g., ‘marker paper’)
- Accurately and completely citing the source of prepublication data and metadata, including the version of the data set
- Being aware that released prepublication data may be associated with quality issues that will be later rectified by the data producers
- Contacting the data producers to discuss publication plans in the case of overlap between planned analyses
- Ensuring that use of data does not harm participants and is in conformity with ethical, legal, and social aspects and approvals
- In case of major data project using substantial, significant or otherwise potentially sensitive prepublication data, users are encouraged to submit a Project application to TS for access to the data (digital Tetiaroa) to facilitate review and collaboration with relevant stakeholders

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